

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 3.4 to AD4.1 – PARC General Survey Interviewer Manual

WP 4

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Technical reference

Work package	WP4 - Monitoring and Exposure
Task	T 4.1 - Human Biomonitoring S4.1.1.1 - Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct
Dissemination level ¹	VITO/ISCIH
Lead Beneficiary/ Responsible AE	SpF
Co-authors	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr
Contributing Participants	Natalie Von Goetz (FOPH); Noelia Dominguez-Morueco (ISCIH); Erika Zardin (STAMI); Margaux Riou (SpF)
Deliverables	30 June 2023
Actual submission date	22 June 2023

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other program participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
Version 1	2023-06-22	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr	
Version 2	2023-07-11	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr	Small adaptations after external review of AD4.1

Table of contents

Technical reference _____	4
Document history _____	5
Table of contents _____	6
Abbreviations _____	7
Introduction and aims _____	8
Information for interviewers _____	9
Interviewer Manual for the Basic questionnaires _____	11
Section 1.01 Personal Information _____	11
Section 1.02 Sociodemographic Information _____	12
Section 1.03 Dietary Habits _____	14
Section 1.04 Lifestyles _____	19
Section 1.05 Residential Environment and Home Exposures _____	23
Section 1.06 Occupation _____	29
Section 1.07 Health _____	34
Interviewer Manual for the Matrix questionnaire _____	38
Questions regarding the sample itself _____	38
Specific questions for the blood sampling _____	40
Specific questions for the Hair sampling _____	41
Recent exposures questions to participants - Diet _____	42
Recent exposures questions to participants - Lifestyles _____	45
Recent exposures questions to participants - Home exposures _____	47
References _____	49

List of Appendices:

Appendix A: Summary table of ISCED 2011 codes and criteria

Appendix B1: Definition of major groups, sub-groups ISCO 2008

Appendix B2: The Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community, abbreviated as NACE [Rev 2]

Appendix C: Food portion sizes gallery

Abbreviations

AMPA	Aminomethylphosphonic Acid
DINCH	Di(isononyl) cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate
DIY	Do-It-Yourself
ECO	Ecological
GPS	Global Positioning System
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
ISCO	International Standard Classification of Occupations
MenuCH	<i>Switzerland</i> - National Nutrition Survey
MOM	Methylmercury-contrOl in expectant Mothers - study
NACE	Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community
PARC	European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
TTP	Time To Pregnancy

Introduction and aims

The present manual contains instructions intended to facilitate the field work. This manual is designed specifically for interviewers in order to be considered as a reference tool at the time of collecting information. It provides a justification of the objective of each question included in the general survey questionnaire. The general survey questionnaire has been designed to collect all the necessary information concerning individual characteristics of the participants and on different sources and routes of exposure to the priority substances selected for each study with the aim to characterize as well as possible the level of exposure to all these substances.

Table 1 shows the list of biomarkers and the priorities in the sample collection that have been set in each age group for PARC general survey.

Table 1: Overview of prioritized substance groups per age group for P4.1.1.2. a_YI_GenHBMSurvey

Children (6-11yrs)	Teenagers (12-17yrs)	Adults (18-39yrs)
	Arsenic species	
Bisphenols	Bisphenols	Bisphenols
Mercury in hair		
Metals (multi-elements) in urine		Metals (multi-elements) in urine
		Metals (multi-elements) in blood
		Pesticides – Glyphosate/AMPA
Pesticides – Pyrethroids	Pesticides – Pyrethroids	Pesticides – Pyrethroids
Pesticides –Neonicotinoids (Acetamiprid)		Pesticides – Neonicotinoids (Acetamiprid)
Pesticides –Organophosphates (chlorpyrifos)	Pesticides –Organophosphates (chlorpyrifos)	Pesticides – Organophosphates (chlorpyrifos)
	PFAS	PFAS
Phthalates & substitutes DINCH	Phthalates & substitutes DINCH	
Cotinine	Cotinine	Cotinine
Creatinine	Creatinine	Creatinine
Specific gravity	Specific gravity	Specific gravity

The list of multielement in metals includes: Arsenic and its compounds, Cadmium, Chrome, Mercury and its organic compound.

Information for interviewers

To ensure that the questionnaires are administered in a standardized way, please follow the considerations listed below:

- This questionnaire only must be applied to the person selected to participate in PARC study.
- Questions and responses must be literally read by the interviewers, always following the fixed order. To dispel misunderstanding among participants, please do speak clear and loud enough and at a normal rate to be adequately heard by the interviewee.
- The response given by the interviewee must be accepted by the interviewer. In those cases, where a certain response is not feasible or convincing the interviewer should formulate the question again to receive a new answer. If not, the given response will be finally accepted by the interviewer.
- All the questions of this questionnaire must be answered by the interviewee. In case the interviewee does not provide a precise response after a reasonable period of time, or refuse to answer, the question will be considered as "Don't know".

Notes for the Matrix questionnaire

- ▶ For all questions requesting to enter a date, please make sure to enter 24:00 h for the "old" day and 0:00 h for the "new" day.
- ▶ Please keep in mind that most of the questions are aimed at the time before sampling. This is one of the aims of this questionnaire: to find out what the participant did directly prior to providing the sample.

Please check if the participant, when answering the questions, has this in mind. It can be helpful to keep reminding the participant gently that this question is directed at the time before sampling. If necessary, give an example like '24 hrs ago is not yesterday around this time now, but yesterday around the time you provided the sample.

Interviewer Manual for the Basic questionnaires

Section 1.01 Personal Information

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
What sex were you assigned at birth?	This question is to assess potential differences in exposure to environmental contaminants between males and females. Sex can be an important factor in determining the absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion of environmental chemicals in the body. Additionally, some chemicals may have specific effects on reproductive health, and sex can play a role in determining susceptibility to these effects.	Sex on original birth certificate will be asked here.
What is your birth date? / What is the child's birth date?	This question is essential to identify potential differences in human exposures, as well as susceptibility associated with the age. Potential determinant of exposure to phthalates, BPA, PFASs, Metals, and pesticides.	Day, month and year of birth will be asked here.
<i>How do you identify yourself with respect to gender?</i>	Gender identity can influence a person's behavior, lifestyle, and occupational choices, which can impact their exposure to environmental chemicals. In addition to biological sex, gender can also influence factors such as dietary choices, personal care product use, and other behaviors that can affect exposure levels.	Gender as a social construct will be asked here.
<i>Do you live with your parents or legal guardian?</i>	This question is to assess whether the adolescent live with their parents or legal guardians which may influence the adolescent way of life.	Please indicate whether or not the participant lives with his/her parents or legal guardian

Section 1.02 Sociodemographic Information

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
In which country were you born? / In which country was the child born?	It is necessary to collect information on participants' country of origin, as it could lead to different exposure levels to priority substances (due to genetic characteristics, lifestyle or dietary habits, among others).	In this question, information on the country where the participants were born will be asked for.
Were your biological parents born in the same country as you? / Were the child's biological parents born in the same country as he/she?	Asking about the participant's parents' country of origin can provide important information about potential differences in exposure to chemicals based on ancestry and ethnicity; In addition, to cultural practices and lifestyle factors.	Information on the participant's biological parents country of origin will be asked for.
How long have you been living ...? Please indicate the number of years (or months if less than 1 year) and the details of your current address (es) Please indicate all addresses if the child is in shared custody/parenting	This question is intended to gather information on internal and external migrations, since it could be associated with changes in chemical exposure levels.	According to geographical characteristics of each country, please ask for the length of time living in this country and the details of the current address. For children/adolescents in shared custody or parenting, all addresses will be completed.
What is the highest level of education you and your partner (if applicable) attained? / What is the highest level of education attained by the parents/legal guardians?	The level of education is a proxy of the socio-economic situation, which could be used to develop an indicator of occupational social class. Determinant of exposure to the priority substances.	Please, indicate the level completed by the interviewee and their partner if applicable. For children, this information will be asked for the parents and legal guardians. When required, check the right category in Appendix A "International Standard Classification of Education" https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/isced-2011-operational-manual/summary-table-of-isced-2011-codes-and-criteria_9789264228368-14-en
What is your current main labour status and your partner's main labour status (if applicable)?	The labour status is also a proxy of the socio-economic situation, which could be used to develop an indicator of occupational social class. Determinant of exposure to the priority substances.	Please note that this question is referred to the labour which the interviewee dedicates most of her/his time to. For children and adolescents living with parents/legal guardians, this information will also be asked for each parent/legal guardian

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>What ethnic origin do you have?</p>	<p>Ethnicity can be a proxy for various socioeconomic factors that can impact exposure levels, such as income, education, and occupation. These factors can influence an individual's exposure to chemicals through factors such as access to healthcare, and housing conditions.</p>	<p>Please, indicate the participant's ethnic group</p>
<p>Which language(s) is (are) spoken at home?</p>	<p>By asking languages spoken at home we can collect additional information on the origin of the participant and also on cultural factors.</p>	<p>Please, indicate the national language (or languages, for countries with several official languages) spoken at home. If other language(s) different from national languages is (are) spoken at home, specify which one(s).</p>

Section 1.03 Dietary Habits

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>How often did you consume the following food categories in the last 12 months?</p>	<p>This question is necessary to assess the overall dietary habits of participants. Certain foodstuffs can be the source of exposure to prioritized substances. Phthalate exposure has been shown to be positively correlated with consumption of: cereal products, fats, fatty dairy products (e.g. butter, cheese), offal, and various sweets (e.g. ice cream, hazelnut spread, and jelly candies) as well as ready meals, fruits and vegetables, fish, meat (poultry) and eggs. Canned food/drinks could be a determinant of the exposure to BPA. Local eggs, fruits and vegetables are sources of exposure to PFASs. Seafood consumption is also a determinant of the exposure to Cd, Cr and Hg. Exposure to ‘toxic’ As has been associated with consumption of rice.</p>	<p>Please note that the period of interest 12 months in order to assess the typical diet. Think about all the food you eat, both meals and snacks, either at home or outside,</p>
<p>How often did you consume the following seafood and fish species items in the last 3 months?</p>	<p>This question is necessary to assess the sea food and fish dietary habits of participants. Seafood consumption is also a determinant of the exposure to Cd, Cr and Hg. The half-life of these metals is around 90 days.</p>	<p>Please specify all amount of foods you consumed including also ingredients of any meal (e.g. salad for sandwiches, cheese for pasta or sandwiches...) Please, show Appendix C “Food portion sizes gallery” to the interviewee to check the portion sizes of each food consumed in the last 3 months. Indicate the frequency of consumption of each food, as well as the portions, according to the pictures included in the gallery.</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>Did you eat fish or other seafood items in the last 7-14 days? How often did the child consume the following seafood and fish species items in the last 7 – 14 days?</p>	<p>It is important in the assessment of exposure to arsenic calculating adjusted mean values, since fish arsenic“ is essentially nontoxic and analytical methods based on total urinary arsenic content may overestimate exposures to arsenic species that are of health concern“ (ATSDR, 2007; Huges et al., 2006). This period of time (7-14 days) before analysis of arsenic is recommended by the US laboratory https://calpoison.org/news/arsenic-poisoning-2011</p>	<p>Please specify all amount of foods you consumed including also ingredients of any meal (e.g. salad for sandwiches, cheese for pasta or sandwiches...) Please, show Appendix C “Food portion sizes gallery” to the interviewee to check the portion sizes of each food consumed in the 7-14 days. Indicate the frequency of consumption of each food, as well as the portions, according to the pictures included in the gallery.</p>
<p>How often did you consume the following food items in the last 12 months?</p>	<p>Asking about a 12-month period of food consumption is done for several reasons: First, it allows to assess the long-term dietary exposure to some chemicals, which can accumulate in the body over time (pesticides, PFAS, metals). It also provides a more comprehensive and accurate picture of a person's dietary habits, as food consumption can vary over time and may be influenced by seasonal changes, availability, and other factors.</p>	<p>Please specify all amount of foods you consumed including also ingredients of any meal (e.g. salad for sandwiches, cheese for pasta or sandwiches...) Please, show Appendix C “Food portion sizes gallery” to the interviewee to check the portion sizes of each food consumed in the last 12 months. Indicate the frequency of consumption of each food, as well as the portions, according to the pictures included in the gallery.</p>
<p>In the past 12 months, how often were the eggs that you ate from your own hens or received/bought from neighbours, friends, family or local growers?</p>	<p>Recent study findings indicate that human exposure to PFAS via consumption of home-produced eggs can be relatively high, even for compounds that have been phased-out decades ago in Europe https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S004565352202776X</p>	<p>Please indicate the frequency in which the participant consume home-produced or local eggs.</p>
<p>How do you usually eat vegetables and fruits?</p>	<p>This question evaluates exposure to pesticides which can leave residues on the skin and flesh of fruits and vegetables and may remain on the surface of the produce, even after washing.</p>	<p>Please indicate the consumption habit of the participant</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>Did you consume organic food in the last 12 months? How often did you usually consume organic food in the last 12 months? Which percentage of your diet is based on organic food? Indicate a percentage for each of the following food items (0%= nothing organic and 100%= all the food consumed is organic)</p>	<p>Organic diet has been found to be associated with decreased level of exposure to pesticides in humans.</p>	<p>Information on the consumption of organic food in the last 12 months (including the main groups of meals) will be collected here. Please note that organic food can be identified by the labelled and specifications in their packaging. Please, select “don’t know” if the interviewee is unable to differentiate organic from non-organic food.</p>
<p>Did you eat vegetables and/or fruit from your own garden or received/bought from neighbours, friends, family or local growers in the last 12 months? If yes, indicate per season the portion you have eaten locally-grown products (0%= nothing and 100%= all fruit/vegetables is from local sources)</p>	<p>This question aims to assess the effect of eating home-grown vegetables and/or fruit could on the exposure levels to pesticides in humans.</p>	<p>If yes, specify the percentage of home-grown vegetables and/or fruit consumed by the interviewee in each of the seasons.</p>
<p>How much water do you drink on average each day? (Do also think of water in hot beverages and soups!)</p>	<p>This question evaluates the amount of water consumed daily by the interviewees.</p>	<p>Please note that the period of interest is 4 weeks in order to assess the current amount of water consumption. Also consider any other beverages you drink at home and outside home, including hot beverages, tea, coffee and soup.</p>
<p>What is the main source of your water for drinking? And water for cooking?</p>	<p>This question is essential to understand what kind of water is consumed most frequently by study participants because the different sources of water have their own bromatological and chemical composition. Together with the home address it provides valuable exposure information. Often, liquids are within bottles with a cap or a layer made out of plastic that is in contact with the liquid. This is why bottled water can potentially be a source of phthalate and BPA exposure. Origin could be also associated with the exposure to PFASs.</p>	<p>This question refers to water consumed at home or elsewhere (e.g., tap water, bottled water). Consider also water use to prepare hot beverages (tea, coffee), and for preparing meals. Please, only indicate the main source of drinking and cooking water.</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>Do you use water purification devices or water filtering systems for your water?</p>	<p>This question evaluates the kind of filters used by the participants at home because filters modify and purify water and consequently they can influence the levels of chemicals of interest.</p>	<p>This refers to any water treatments done at home, do not include treatments performed by the municipality.</p>
<p>In which of the following bottling types do you usually consume beverages? Please consider all beverages (fruit juices, ice tea, soft drinks...) including water (Multiple answers possible)</p>	<p>This question assesses the possible exposure to prioritized substances from food contact materials through food (cross contamination). Often, liquid containers have a cap or an internal layer made out of plastic that is in contact with the liquid they contain. This is why bottled water can potentially be a source of phthalate and BPA exposure. Decorated drinking glass are source of cadmium.</p>	<p>Please note that and type of selected material referred only to possible sources of prioritized substances. Other sources such as aluminum or glass are also possible.</p>
<p>Do you use the following containers for keeping the food in the refrigerators or for longer-time storage elsewhere? If yes, how often do you use it?</p>	<p>This question evaluates the possible exposure to prioritized substances (e.g. PFASs, BPA) from food contact materials.</p>	<p>Please note that information on the use of each type of containers has to be collected. Containers used for general food storage (cold and non-cold storage) are included here.</p>
<p>Do you use the following containers for preparing or heating your food in the microwave oven? If yes, how often do you use it?</p>	<p>This question evaluates the possible exposure to prioritized substances (e.g. PFASs, BPA) from food contact materials (cross contamination).</p>	<p>Please note that multiple answers are possible and type of selected material referred only to possible sources of prioritized substances. Other sources such as aluminum or glass are possible.</p>
<p>What materials do you use as cookware for cooking and frying (e.g. pots, pans, fryer, robots, making bread machine etc.)</p>	<p>This question evaluates the possible exposure to prioritized substances (e.g. BPA, PFASs) from cross contamination from other food products.</p>	<p>Please note that participants can select multiple type of materials, most of them considered as possible sources of prioritized substances, other ones such as aluminum or glass are possible.</p>
<p>Do you consume dietary supplements (e.g. vitamins and minerals)? If yes, please indicate type, frequency and duration.</p>	<p>Human metabolism of some xenobiotics could be affected/modulated by the concentration of vitamins.</p>	<p>Information on vitamins and supplements (not for medicines), has to be collected here. When appropriate (e.g. a product not included in the listed options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of the product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee has not a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't know.</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>How often do you eat dishes from communal catering, such as from a canteen, dining hall or cafeteria in the last 4 weeks?</p>	<p>This question evaluates the exposure to material possibly containing phthalates, BPA, PFASs and other priority substances.</p>	<p>Please note participant’s habit of catering consumption</p>
<p>Did the child eat any of the following toddler foods in the last month (if yes, please specify the frequency)?</p>	<p>This question assesses exposure to priority substances such as bisphenols and phthalates through food contact.</p>	<p>Please note that participants can select multiple type of food contact materials, most of them considered as possible sources of prioritized substances.</p>
<p>In the last 4 weeks, did you consume fast food and ready meals (prepared dishes as frozen pizza and the like) (please consider also beverages)? If yes, how was it packed and how often did he/she consume it?</p>	<p>This question evaluates exposure to food contact materials possibly containing phthalates, BPA, PFASs and other priority substances.</p>	<p>Please note that participants can select multiple type of food contact materials, most of them considered as possible sources of prioritized substances. However, other food contact materials such as aluminum or glass are possible.</p>

Section 1.04 Lifestyles

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>In relation to smoking habits, which of the following options best describes your situation? Please, specify all the information for the situation chosen.</p>		<p>Please, indicate the situation of the participant in relation to smoking habits. Specify the type of product and the frequency of smoking (occasionally, daily and ex-smokers). If the participant has never smoked, 'no' can be ticked under point 1.1 and skip the remaining parts of the question.</p>
<p>How many people living in this house smoke or vape regularly (indoors)? For each of them, please indicate the average number of cigarettes smoked and the average number of e-cigarettes' puffs vaped per day indoors</p>	<p>Information on smoking habits and passive exposure to tobacco smoke has to be collected since these are well known sources of exposure to a wide variety of substances such as PAHs, Cd, Cr, BPA and anilines. The concentration of nicotine metabolites has been shown to be significantly associated with the concentration of phthalates.</p>	<p>Please, complete this table for all of the household members that smoke inside the home.</p>
<p>In general, how long, on a daily average, do you usually spend in the following indoor places where people smoke?</p>		<p>Here it is important to ask only for house where people smoke, and elsewhere</p>
<p>Do people who visit this house smoke indoors?</p>		<p>Here, ask for the frequency in which people visiting the house smoke (indoors)</p>
<p>How often do you consume alcoholic beverages?</p>	<p>Alcohol has been identified as an important confounder in many epidemiological studies. Hence, information on alcohol consumption in the last year has to be collected.</p>	<p>Indicate the frequency of alcoholic beverages consumption.</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>How often did you use the following cosmetic and hygiene products in the last month? For each product, please indicate the commercial brand you mostly use.</p>	<p>Personal care products and cosmetics are widely used. Complete information on the use of these products is needed to a proper characterization of the exposure in humans. Phthalate exposure has been shown to be positively correlated with the use of deodorant, body lotion, anti-ageing cream and perfume as well as make-up and cosmetic products in general. BPA exposure could be also associated with the use of these products. Specific types, such as water resistant make up, nail polish... could be associated with the exposure to PFASs.</p>	<p>Complete information on personal care products and cosmetic used by the interviewee in the last month has to be collected. For each listed product, please indicate yes/no, and the commercial brand for those used by the interviewees. If the interviewee cannot give an answer for a product, please invite him/her to check whether the mentioned product is available at home at the time of the interview. The best would be to show a list of the cosmetic products in question and let the participant to read it along with the interviewer. This would make it easier and quicker to point out the cosmetic items used.</p>
<p>Consumers more and more often pay attention to whether the cosmetics are natural. Do you pay attention to the composition of the products you use or do you select products that are advertised as made without parabens, phthalates, sulphates...?</p>	<p>This information may be used as a stratifier for analysing the biomarker levels but will also help learn about participants' literacy about chemicals and their behaviour about them.</p>	<p>Complete information on the participant behavior towards products advertised as chemical free products.</p>
<p>Did you carry out any of the following activities as DIY (Do-It-Yourself) activities or hobbies and/or were you exposed to any of these substances in these activities in the last 3 months? (Please, do not count your professional activity)</p>	<p>Some hobbies and DIY activities involve the use of certain products which could affect exposure to priority substances. This question will help to explore the relationship between the products used in the last month and the exposure levels to the studied analytes.</p>	<p>Please note that this question refers to exposures occurred in the last month. For each group of products, indicate if they have been used by the interviewee. When applicable (e.g. a product not included in the given options or not sure about the right category), then select other products and specify the name of the product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee has not a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't Know. For those questions covering the use of inks (e.g. tattoos), please note that they refer to people using these substances (e.g. tattoos artists) but not to people receiving a tattoo (this aspect is covered below)</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>Have you done any body modifications (excluding medical interventions) in the last 5 years? If yes, specify the number, the size, the color and the age of each modification.</p>	<p>This question is used to identify persons with body modifications. They may need to be treated separately in some analysis. Body modifications, such as piercings, tattoos (including different colours), artificial joints could be a source of exposure to certain metals (e.g. cadmium, chromium)</p>	<p>This question excludes any medical intervention done for the body. Please, specify the colour(s) of the tattoo, when applicable. The timing for each body modification should be reported as accurately as possible. If the number of days cannot be precisely recalled, ask at least for the number of months and years. In case the number of months is difficult to provide, at least the number of years should be recorded. In case the participant had to go several times to complete one tattoo, it is reported here the age on the very first application.</p>
<p>Do you have any artificial joints, pins, plates, metal suture material, or other types of metal objects in your body? (Do not include piercings, crowns, dental braces or retainers, shrapnel, or bullets.)</p>	<p>This question is used to identify participants with artificial joints etc. in their body. These may need to be treated separately in some analysis.</p>	<p>The interviewee should answer “Yes” if he/she has any of the listed objects in their body.</p>
<p>How often do you usually wear metallic jewelry or watch bracelet, excluding gold, silver or platinum jewelry/bracelet?</p>	<p>Wearing metallic jewellery on the skin could be a source of exposure to certain metals, specially chromium.</p>	<p>Please, specify here if the interviewee wear metallic jewellery and frequency.</p>
<p>Please, indicate how much time on a daily average, you use electronic devices such as mobile phones, computers, tablets, GPS... in the last month?</p>	<p>This question aims to collect information on use of electronic devices, since BPA and FR are frequently used in the manufacturing processes.</p>	<p>Please, indicate the overall time average dedicated to handle electronical devices, including portable and desk devices, in the last month.</p>
<p>How long do you dedicate to sport and/or physical activities? Which of the following options best describes your current physical exercise?</p>	<p>This question aims to collect information on general physical exercise. Physical exercise might affect some factors related to metabolism of xenobiotics in humans, as has been observed in epidemiological studies, which could lead to differences in exposure levels to these compounds.</p>	<p>Please indicate approximate number of hours per day. This question includes information on overall physical exercise (intensity, frequency, duration). Please, note that intensive exercise refers to any sweating activity that also makes breathing harder.</p>
<p>How often (times per day) do you wash your hands?</p>	<p>Frequency of hand washing is a determinant of the exposure to different compounds (e.g. BPA, phthalates)</p>	<p>Please indicate here the times per day.</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>Do you have a habit of putting objects made of plastic (e.g. pens, glasses or toys) in your mouth and chewing on them? If yes, please specify the frequency</p>	<p>Determinant of exposure to phthalates, among other substances.</p>	<p>Ask here if the interviewee has habit of chewing on plastic objects.</p>
<p>Do you wear regularly plastic or rubber shoes such as e.g. flip-flops, beach shoes, swimming shoes, Crocs ® or clogs without socks?</p>	<p>Rubber shoes often contain phthalates. Direct contact with (sweating) skin can therefore be a source of phthalate exposure.</p>	<p>Please, ask for the regular use of the type of plastic or rubber shoes mentioned. The use is limited to cases wearing shoes without socks. Regular use means more than 3 times per week.</p>

Section 1.05 Residential Environment and Home Exposures

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>In which area is your home located?</p>	<p>This question aims to characterize the environment where the participant lives, as differences could exist in human exposure associated with the area of residence.</p>	<p>This question has to be answered according to the area in which the home is located. Please, only one from the given options must be selected (best fit).</p>
<p>Is your current home address and/or previous home address located near any of these facilities?</p>	<p>It is necessary to collect information on facilities considered as potential sources of exposure to pollutants, which might lead to differences in human exposure levels. Likewise, this question provides information on the general characteristics of the living environment (e.g. heavily industrialized area, agricultural fields...) Please, ask only for those facilities located near the participant's home (300 m). Multiple answers are possible.</p>	<p>If the concept of distance is not well understood by the interviewee, some explanation can be given as: "facilities within 15 minutes walking distance from your home". When appropriate (e.g. facilities not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of other facilities located near household.</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>Does your house have garden and/or vegetable garden? Has your garden/vegetable garden been treated with pesticides in the last 12 months? Has your house (inside) or your workplace been treated with herbicides, fungicides and/or insecticides in the last 4 weeks?</p>	<p>Is essential to collect information on the presence of a garden or vegetable garden at home, as well as on the use of products to treat, since they could be a potential source of exposure to pesticides.</p> <p>The use of pesticides/insecticides at the workplace/house could be associated with increased levels of exposure to pesticides.</p>	<p>if the answer is “No”, all the sub-questions under can be skipped. If the answer is “Yes”, please complete all of the sub-questions. Here, the use of pesticides/insecticides in the last 12 months is required</p> <p>Here, the use of pesticides/insecticides at workplace/house (inside) in the last 4 weeks is required.</p>
<p>Who applies pesticides in your home or garden?</p>	<p>This question determines who applied the pesticides and whether or not the participants were directly exposed to the pesticides.</p>	<p>Please indicate who applies pesticides in the garden: the participant him/herself, a member of the household, a professional or other.</p>
<p>In the last 12 months, were insecticide/pesticide products used to control or repel pest problems in your garden? (e.g. snails/slugs, weeds, mosses/lichens, other garden pests/insects).</p>	<p>Products to repel insects could be a source of exposure to pesticides</p>	<p>This question refers to products such as sprays, liquids, used in the last 12 months in the garden</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>What is the main water source for your home garden irrigation?</p>	<p>This question is essential to understand what type of water most frequently used by the study participants in their gardens is important because different water sources have their own bromatological and chemical composition. Depending on the water source used, edible garden produce is likely to be contaminated by a range of chemical substances.</p>	<p>Indicate the option that best fits from the given options</p>
<p>Which of the following options best describes your home...?</p>	<p>Asking for home types allows gathering additional information on the characteristics of the dwelling and the environment where the participant live. Moreover, the home type could contribute to different exposure to contaminants (e.g. floor level, isolation...)</p>	<p>Indicate the option that best fits from the given options. When necessary, specify other home types. Please note that semi-detached house is a single-family home that is built to share one common wall with the adjacent home, having both of them the same design. On the other hand, townhouses are traditionally row houses with two or more floors, where homes are connected, on both sides and on all levels.</p>
<p>What materials are used for most of the floor coverings in your home?</p>	<p>The floor covering is considered as an important source of indoor exposure to certain compounds, especially phthalates, BPA and PFASs. Furthermore, floor covering favoring dust accumulation could be a way for humans to be exposed to other pollutants at home. Phthalates and flame retardants are used as plasticizers(softeners) in floor covering. They are volatile and can be found in house dust, too. One of the newer phthalates, DPHP, is used in both carpet coating and also inside cars. The more space in the flat has PVC floor covering, the bigger is the surface for possible phthalates exposure. Regarding flame retardants, despite some compounds have been forbidden (e.g. PBDEs), exposure to other organohalogen and organophosphorus compounds could occur at home</p>	<p>This question aims to collect information on the main type of materials used to cover more than 50% of the floor. When appropriate (e.g. floor covering not included in the given options or not sure about the right category), specify the name of other floor coverings given by the interviewee. If a clear response is not obtained, then select Don't Know. Synthetic or natural fiber with plastic backing refers to fiber that is fixed on a flat, sometimes bendable surface made out of a rubber or plastic. This surface is often not seen easily as it is the layer applied to the ground (the backside or backing), with the fiber side facing upwards.</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

	due to the previous presence of these materials in floor coverings.	
Are you in charge of the general cleaning of your home? (General cleaning includes vacuum cleaning, mopping - use of cleaners/chemicals, disinfectant products in water, sweeping, dusting) In that case specify the percentage you are in charge of	House cleaning is associated with the concentration of substances, including chemical pollutants inside home, such as phthalates, among others. This variable might affect human exposure indoors, since house cleaning involves the mobilization and elimination of dust-borne chemicals deposited in floor, windows, etc. House cleaning might affect human exposure to substances accumulated indoors, especially by those in charge of the general cleaning, due to their direct contact.	Please, specify the contribution of the interviewee to the general cleaning of the house (if he/she has a partial contribution, ask for an estimation of the percentage of the workload usually done).
Do you clean your home with water? If yes, please specify the frequency.	The frequency of cleaning with water is more effective to remove house dust and improve the indoor air quality.	Please indicate whether water washing is used to clean the house. If so, please specify the frequency of use.
Do you use vacuum cleaner for general cleaning of your home? If yes, please, specify type and frequency of use	The use of vacuum cleaner for house cleaning involves the mobilization of substances accumulated in domestic dust. This might affect the concentrations of circulating compounds inside home (e.g. flame retardants and phthalates), and therefore, the exposure of residents to these compounds.	Please, indicate if a vacuum cleaner is used for house cleaning. When appropriate, specify the frequency of use, as well as the type of filter. Note that water filters refer to those vacuum cleaners having a container for water, while air filters do not need water for working but a bag or a tank where the dust is accumulated.
In the last month, were any of the cleaning products listed below used in your home, at least once a week? If yes, Please specify if the cleaning product generally used is a classical or eco-friendly product (product featuring an ECO-label on the package)	Certain household cleaning products contain chemical substances which residents could be exposed to (e.g. PFASs in furniture polish/ specific cleaning agents/ impregnation/ coating agents/ paints). Hence, a proper characterization of the exposure via questionnaire to these products is needed to identify their potential contribution on	This question aims to identify those products used at home at least once a week in the last month, irrespective of the person in charge of their application. For those products used, please specify if it is a classical or eco-friendly product. Eco-friendly products refer to those products without chemical substances in their composition (or

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

	human exposure.	reduced concentrations). They can be identified by the labelled and specifications in their packaging. Please, select “don’t know” if the interviewee is unable to differentiate classical from eco-friendly products. If applicable (e.g. a product not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee does not have a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't Know.
How much time do you spend on average in the following places (referred to weekdays and weekends)?	The time spent on a daily basis in different environments will provide essential information on potential sources of exposure to contaminants in humans, as well as on their contribution on total exposure burden. Newer cars’ interiors can be a source for phthalate exposure (e.g. DPHP), BPA or FR. The newer the car, the more likely a higher exposure. The more time spent in a new car, the more likely is higher exposure.	Please, compile information on time spent in each of the given environments, during weekdays and weekends. Time should refer to an average of time based on the daily habits of the interviewee. ‘In your car’ refers to the total time spent seated in the car with the doors closed, no matter if the engine is turned on or not.
Did you have any of these situations at home? [Breakage of a mercury thermometer] [Breakage of an energy-saving lamp] Which one(s) of these clean-up actions did you take? Please choose all that apply	This question assesses accidental exposure to mercury following damage to an object containing mercury (mercury thermometer, energy-saving lamp), the date on which the event occurred and the cleaning actions carried out that will influence exposure.	Please note whether the participant has been confronted with these situations, for how long and the actions they have taken to remedy them. Several actions are possible
Please, complete the following information about redecorations and renovations made in your home. Is your home currently being renovated? (Major renovations: e.g. new walls, floor, windows...) Has your home been renovated in the last year? Has your home been redecorated in the last year?	Renovations and redecorations at home entail the use of a wide of variety of compounds, such as paints, varnish, metals, and plastics, among others. This could contribute to chemical exposure in people living in houses where recent renovations and redecorations were conducted. Especially renovation can include the exchange of floor or wall covering. The procedure of removing the former covering with a new one with a potentially higher concentration of phthalates, BPA could	Please, consider only renovations conducted in the last year, and redecorations in the last year. Renovations refer to major changes made at home for a better state, such as removing floor or windows, rebuilding walls or roof, remodelling kitchen or bathroom... Redecorations refer to changes in decorative scheme or appearance, such as applying paint, varnish, changing wallpapers, among others.

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

	increase exposure to these compounds.	
How is your house usually ventilated? For each option, please specify frequency of use (months/year in which mechanical systems are used; hours/day for window ventilation by season; ventilation grilles in windows/doors or walls)	Ventilation at home (mechanical or manual) is related with the exchange of circulating compounds, affecting to indoor concentrations of these compounds at home, and consequently to human exposure levels.	Please, ask for ways of the ventilation of home, and their frequency of use. Please note that mechanical ventilation usually entails the presence of electromechanical systems (e.g. fans) to drive air flow inside and outside home. In case this mechanical system is automatically working, then indicate Always on in the questionnaire.
Do you have any pets at home or did you have any pets at home in the last 12 months? If so, specify type and number	Pets are considered as a source of home exposure to certain compounds (allergens, pesticides, parabens, among others), because of the deposition or accumulation of these substances in the hair. Likewise, this question could be also helpful for studying the relationship between having pets at home and the development of allergic or atopic diseases, such as asthma, eczema...	Note down if certain animals are present at home, and their number. Please, specify other animals not included but reported by the interviewee.

Section 1.06 Occupation

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
What is your occupation/profession?	Participants would give information about their occupation. Researchers will link the information with the ISCO codes.	Annex B1 includes information code nomination for the International Standard Classification of Occupations version 2008, ISCO-08) https://www.ilo.org/public/english/bureau/stat/isco/docs/publication08.pdf
Please, describe your current job:	Job description gives information about the type of work where possible exposures could occur.	Detailed description of work tasks is important to correctly interpret the participants' exposure conditions.
How long have you been doing this job? Specify years (or months if less than one year)	Length of time working is important when assessing effects of occupational exposures	Total working time in this job in years and months is asked.
Do you come into contact with the following substances at your current job? NOTE: contact can occur via the skin and/or by inhalation.	This question is essential to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	It is important to let participants enough time to think about the possible exposure to these substances. Category of chemicals is listed considering various exposure conditions. Some of the priority substances under PARC are mentioned separately in a specified exposure category.

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>Combustion products, including gasoline/diesel exhausts, ash or soot</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as and to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Combustion products including fine particles have an impact on PAHs, heavy metals, ... exposure. Please, select from the list or otherwise specify the work where you come into contact with combustion products (e.g. aluminum production, chimney sweeping, coking plants, firefighting/ fire practice/ fire prevention training, foundry industry, garage work, heating/thermal power plants, metallurgic industry, mining, vehicle inspection, vehicle depots, waste incineration)</p>
<p>Metals (eg. Mercury, Lead, Cadmium, Chromium, others)</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with metals. Specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.) Identification of individual compound is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Metallic dust could be a source of exposure to hazardous (heavy) metals</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Paints/ coatings including varnishes	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the paint and its ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
Printing inks	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the ink and its ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Please, specify the work where you come into contact with printing inks (e.g. ink production, printing industry, other job, which?).
Solvents	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of solvents and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
Plasticizers	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the plasticizers (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Plasticizers could contain e.g. phthalates, which are priority substances under PARC.
Pesticides, biocides or disinfection products (herbicides, fungicides, insecticides or bactericides)	The question aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of each of the pesticides and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Pesticides are priority substances under PARC general survey. Biocides and disinfection products are priority substances under PARC occupational survey.

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Cosmetics or hair treatment products (hair dyes, etc.)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of cosmetics or hair treatment products/hair dyes and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
Polymers production (monomers)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Identification of specific rubber chemicals (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Please, specify the work where you come into contact with polymers.
Flame retardants	Flame retardants are priority substances under PARC occupational surveys..	Identification of each of the flame retardants and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
Photoresist/antireflective coatings	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of each of the photoresist/antireflective coatings and their ingredients (name, CAS- number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
Other hazardous materials, hazardous waste or other chemicals (e.g. contaminated soil renovation)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of other hazardous materials, hazardous waste or other chemicals (name, CAS- number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. These could include e.g. various mixtures, which are priority substances under PARC.
Other compounds	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of each other compound used (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>In the working environment in which you perform working tasks/activities are there technical risk management measures (e.g. local exhaust ventilation, compartmentalisation of the exposure source...) available?</p>	<p>This question provides information on collective protective measures in the workplace in general.</p>	<p>Please, specify the type of measures used (e.g. general ventilation, local ventilation, compartmentalization)</p>
Occupational history		
<p>Please list each of the previous jobs where you have worked, over / back to the past 10 years: For each job, specify the substance which you came in contact with.</p> <p>Exposure to substances</p>	<p>The industry sector is needed to classify the field of work. Job description gives information about the type of work where possible exposures can occur. The working period is important when assessing effects of exposure.</p> <p>This column ‘exposure to substances’ is essential to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>The Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community, abbreviated as NACE (NACE Rev. 2) is included in Appendix B2 at the end of this document (main classes and sub- classification). Detailed description of work tasks is important to correctly interpret the participants' exposure conditions.</p> <p>The total working time in this job (in years and months) is asked.</p> <p>It is important to let participants enough time to think about the possible exposure to these substances. Please use the category list in question 5</p>
Pesticides Occupational exposure and history		
<p>From the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures</p> <p>In your previous jobs, have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures)?</p>	<p>This question aims to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions to pesticides in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring</p>	<p>Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with pesticides, the period of exposure and use of PPE.</p> <p>Identification of specific task is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring.</p>

Section 1.07 Health

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Anthropometric measurements	Anthropometric measurements are indicators of body composition. The BMI has been shown to be significantly correlated with exposure to some phthalates, bisphenols, PFAS, Arsenic (Abuawad et al., 2021)	Record the self-reported height in cm without shoes. Record the self-reported weight in kg without clothes and shoes.
Do you have amalgam fillings/dental sealant in your teeth?	This question is used to identify persons with amalgam fillings and dental sealant. They may need to be treated separately in some analysis. Dental sealant is a determinant of exposure to BPA, while amalgam fillings could be a source of exposure to metals.	Please note that a filling is expected to last for as many as ten years, whereas the average life expectancy of a dental sealant is no longer than a year. Sealants are usually provided to children. If person reports that he/she has any amalgam fillings, the number of teeth which have the filling should be recorded as the time when the filling was last time placed/removed.
Do you use glasses and/or contact eye lenses?	Potential determinant of the exposure to BPA.	Use of glasses or contact lenses has to be collected here.
Have you or any of your biological family members (Father, mother, siblings, grand-mother, grand-father...) been diagnosed by a medical doctor with any of the following diseases or conditions? If yes, has it occurred within the last 12 months, Please specify how old was the participant when this was first diagnosed.	The information about diagnosed diseases is an indicator about disease prevalence and disease history.	The interviewee is asked to provide answer to all diseases on the list and if he/she says “Yes”, then ask and record the age when the disease was diagnosed for the first time. If the interviewee says that he/she has been diagnosed for any other disease(s) not listed, this should be recorded at the end under ‘Other diseases or conditions’
If you answered “Yes” for cancer, please specify what kind of cancer	The information about cancer types is an indicator of specific cancer prevalence. Human exposure to certain chemical compounds could present a risk of developing cancer (e.g.FR, Arsenic, Pesticides, etc.)	This question is asked only for those who self- reported to have or have had any cancer. In case of having had more than one cancer at different sites, record all different cancers reported.

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>During the past two weeks, have you used any medicines or homeopathic medicines?</p>	<p>This question provides information about medication use in general. This information is needed to define does person have a specific disease together with information about diagnosed diseases.</p>	<p>This question asks about the use of medicines and homeopathic medicines. All medicines or homeopathic medicines used in the past two weeks should be recorded as accurately as the interviewee recall this information. Please indicate the commercial name, condition, dose, frequency of use and starting/ending date.</p>
<p>Which of the following options best describe your menstrual cycle? What age did you get your period for the first time? Age at menarche Are you currently on your period?</p>	<p>Information on menstrual cycle and menopause will be collected here, since it could affect the bioaccumulation of priority substances in women (e.g. PFASs (Lum et al., 2017)</p>	<p>This question is asked from women only. Please, collect information on the current situation. Menopause refers to the absence of menstrual periods for 12 consecutive months</p>
<p>Have you ever been pregnant? (Including current pregnancy, live births, miscarriages, stillbirths, tubal pregnancies or abortions)</p>	<p>This question provides information on the number of pregnancies.</p>	<p>This question is asked for women only. If the interviewee replies that she has ever been pregnant, ask the number of pregnancies including possible current pregnancy, live births, miscarriages, stillbirths, tubal pregnancies and abortions.</p>
<p>Please, complete the following information for each of your pregnancies</p>	<p>This question provides detailed information on each pregnancy.</p>	<p>This question is asked for women only. For each pregnancy, information is needed about the outcome: abortion, live birth, polyembryotic or birth defects have to be recorded.</p>
<p>Have you ever been diagnosed with preeclampsia for any of your pregnancies?</p>	<p>This question provides detailed information on pregnancy. Concentrations of certain compounds in humans could present a risk in the development of preeclampsia (e.g. Phthalates, Bisphenols: (Cantonwine et al., 2016)).</p>	<p>This question is asked for women only.</p>
<p>Are you breast feeding or have breastfed? If so, please indicate the length of breastfeeding. For women with several children, specify total months of breastfeeding. (Please note that breast feeding includes pumping of breast milk)</p>	<p>This question provides information about breast feeding history, since it could affect the concentrations of certain compounds in humans (e.g. PFASs, FR).</p>	<p>This question is asked from women only. Women with several children have to specify total months of breastfeeding.</p>
<p>Are you currently pregnant? If yes, how long have you had unprotected sexual intercourse before becoming pregnant?</p>	<p>This question provides information about pregnancy status of female participants. It is needed to identify pregnant women as they may need to be treated separately in some analysis. Time To Pregnancy could be affected by exposure to substances such as phthalates (HBM4EU D14.2), pesticides</p>	<p>This question is asked for women only. <i>Time To Pregnancy TTP is defined as the number of months of unprotected intercourse that elapse before conception occurs.</i> Please indicate the time spent having unprotected intercourse that elapse before conception occurs</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>Have there been time period when you have attempted to have a child but have not succeeded or it took over 12 months to succeed?</p>	<p>This question provides information on fertility problems. Exposure to pesticides could have an effect on reproductive health (Fucic et al., 2021)</p>	<p>This question is asked for women only.</p> <p>This question refers to attempts to get pregnant without success or when it took over 12 months to succeed. If person replies ‘Yes’, the further question to ask is when was the last time this happened (in years) is asked.</p>
<p>Have you ever been examined or been treated for infertility?</p>	<p>This question provides information on type of the fertility problems.</p>	<p>This question is asked for women only.</p>
<p>What was the reason for your infertility?</p>	<p>This question provides information on type of the fertility problems.</p>	<p>This question is asked for women only.</p> <p>This question refers to the fertility problems listed in the questionnaire.</p>
<p>Have there been time period when you have attempted to have a child but have not succeeded or it took over 12 months to succeed?</p>	<p>This question provides information about fertility problems.</p>	<p>This question is asked from men only.</p> <p>This question refers to attempts to get pregnant without success or when it took over 12 months to succeed. If person replies ‘Yes’, further question on when was the last time this happened (in years) is asked.</p>
<p>Have you ever been examined or been treated for infertility?</p>	<p>This question provides information regarding fertility problems.</p>	<p>This question is asked from men only.</p> <p>This question refers to attempts to have a child without getting it or when it took over 12 months to succeed. If person replies ‘Yes’, the further question to ask is when was the last time this happened (in years).</p>
<p>What was the reason for your infertility?</p>	<p>This question provides information on fertility problems.</p>	<p>This question is asked for men only.</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>What is the child’s head circumference? What was the child’s weight at birth (in g)</p>	<p>Anthropometric measurements are indicators of body composition.</p> <p>Exposure to a number of chemicals can lead to low birth weight (<2500 g), including pesticides, cadmium, bisphenols (Chevrier and Béranger, 2018)</p>	<p>Record the self-reported head circumference in cm</p> <p>Record the self-reported weight in g without clothes and shoes.</p>
<p>What was the child’s mother’s age at his/her birth?</p>	<p>Maternal age is also a risk factor for abnormal intrauterine fetal development.</p>	<p>Please indicate the child's mother's age at birth</p>
<p>Did the mother of the child smoke while pregnant of him/her?</p>	<p>Smoking during pregnancy has an impact on fetal development and can cause health problems in children right up to adulthood</p>	<p>Please note the mother's smoking status during pregnancy.</p>
<p>Had the child been breastfed when he/she was a baby? If yes, for how long had he/she been breastfed? Specify years or months, if less than one year</p>	<p>This question provides information about breast feeding history, since it could affect the concentrations of certain compounds in humans</p>	<p>Please specify if mother is breastfeeding only or with supplementation</p>
<p>What was the child’s gestational age at birth (in weeks)? The gestational age describes the time elapses between the first day of the mother’s last menstrual cycle to the birth date. A normal pregnancy can range from 38 to 42 weeks. Infants born before 37 weeks are considered premature.</p>	<p>Exposure to certain chemical substances can lead to premature birth including phthalates and pesticides ((Brinchmann et al., 2018))</p>	<p>Please indicate the child’s gestational age at birth (in weeks)</p>

Interviewer Manual for the Matrix questionnaire

Questions regarding the sample itself

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS	
<p>Has the urine sample been delivered?</p> <p>Has the blood sample been taken?</p> <p>Has the hair sample been collected?</p> <p>Please indicate the reason for missing submission of the urine/blood/hair sample</p>		To be answered by Interviewer: If this question is answered with no, the questionnaire does not have to be applied. Depending on the individual study design, a reschedule of a sampling date has to be appointed in this case.	
Was the urine sample collected in the provided container?		To be answered by Interviewer: the sample should be discarded if another container than the provided one has been used to collect the sample.	
Is there a sampling label on the container?		To be answered by Interviewer: Check if there is a visible, readable label on the sample container containing information about date and time the sample was taken. Can be merged with U4 if only one label exists.	
Is there a label with the correct participant ID on the container?		To be answered by the interviewer: Check if there is a visible, readable label with the participant ID (cross-check with IDs noted down on questionnaires) on the container. Can be merged with U3 if only one label exists.	
When was the urine sample obtained?		<p>These questions all serve to provide background information on if and how the blood or urine sample has been obtained and handled in the participant's home.</p> <p>Asking the participant for the last time he or she urinated before providing the urine sample is important as a plausibility check and might be useful to explain characteristics of the sample.</p>	To be answered by Interviewer: Check if the date and time has been noted down on the container and write it down in the questionnaire or ask the participant.
When was the blood sample obtained?			

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>Is it really the first urine after waking up?</p> <p>Please indicate the reason for missing submission of the morning urine sample</p>		<p>Only to be asked when first morning urine is collected. If the time of the sampling is not in the hours of the morning, meaning up to a max. 12 pm, ask the participant(s) whether this time is correct and whether it is really the first urine after waking up.</p>
<p>When did you last urinate before urine sample collection (date and time)?</p>		<p>Note down the date and time the participant last urinated before collecting the sample.</p>
<p>How was the sample stored at home before collection?</p>		<p>To be answered by the participant: It is important to know if the sample has been cooled or not during the time between sampling and interviewer appointment.</p>
<p>Is the morning urine sample complete? Complete means that all morning urine- entire bladder emptying - was collected for the urine sample? Please indicate the reason for incomplete morning urine sample</p>		<p>This question should be directed to participant only if the study is foreseen to use containers big enough to collect all morning urine. Only to be asked when first morning urine is collected.</p>
<p>Were there any peculiarities with the sample or participant's answers?</p>	<p>This question serves to document anything worth documentation.</p>	<p>To be answered by the interviewer: If you noticed anything in particular (e.g. the sample has been handled a certain way) please note it down here.</p>

Specific questions for the blood sampling

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>What total amount was sampled? Please specify which tubes</p>		<p>Enter here the gross volume of blood taken in milliliters. Please indicate here the tubes used: Plastic serum vacutainer 4mL Glass serum vacutainer 5mL EDTA vacutainer 6mL</p>
<p>If the gross volume was taken in sub- samples: How many sub-samples were taken?</p>		<p>Enter here the number of tubes and volume of blood in each tube in milliliters.</p>

Specific questions for the Hair sampling

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
What is the length of the hair sampled? (Length from the scalp)		This question serves a quality control and refers to the total length of hair sampled. The fieldworker Will take the measurement after receiving the sample. The portion of sample will be carefully measured in the laboratory.
What is the natural colour of the hair?		Enter here the natural color of the participant's hair.
What is the natural structure of the hair?		Enter here the structure of the hair: [] Black/dark brown [] Brown [] Blond/fair [] Red/strawberry blond
When was the hair last washed?		Choose between the date options provided – Today, yesterday, before yesterday
How many days ago?		This is to be filled only when they select before yesterday. Please enter here the number of days past since the last wash

Recent exposures questions to participants - Diet

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	ASSOCIATED SUBSTANCE GROUP(S)	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>When was your last meal before urine sample collection? When was your last meal before blood sample collection?</p>			<p>To be answered by the participant: Note down the date and time the participant last ate (important: small snacks count as well!) before collecting the sample.</p>
<p>Before providing the sample, when did you last eat any food belonging to the following food groups?</p>	<p>For some substance groups, it is important to learn when the last possibility for exposure with this substance group took place, i.a. when the participant last ate a potentially contaminated food item. Food items can be a source of exposure for different and various substances. Food items have been grouped according to the groups found in the basic questionnaire.</p>	<p>Phthalates & substitutes: Fast food, ready meals (in plastic packaging), fats, dairy products Bisphenols: Canned food Heavy metals: Fish, seafood, game meat, offal, snails, cereal products, seaweeds, mushrooms, leafy vegetables PFAS (measured in blood): Eggs, Popcorn (microwavable cooked in bags) (Susmann et al., 2019), fruits, vegetables Arsenic: Rice and rice-based products</p>	<p>Important: Please keep reminding the participant that this question is directed at the time before sampling (up to 72 hrs). If the participant names food items, but not groups kindly ask if they could sort the items into one of the groups.</p>
<p>When did you last take dietary supplements (algae, spirulina, vitamins, minerals, omega-3 fatty acids etc...) during the past 24 hrs prior to sampling? If yes, please specify supplement</p>	<p>Some dietary supplements contain compounds that can influence the biomarkers being measured. To ensure accurate interpretation of HBM results, it is crucial to collect comprehensive information about participants' supplement intake prior to sampling.</p>		<p>Participants should disclose the specific supplements taken, including brand names and dosages.</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>Before providing the sample, when did you last drink any beverages belonging to the following list?</p>	<p>For some substance groups, it is important to learn when the last possibility for exposure with this substance group took place, i.e. when the participant last drank a potentially contaminated beverage. Beverages can be a source of exposure for different and various substances.</p>	<p>Cadmium: Sakè, vegetable (tomato) juice. Metals: barley coffee, beer, fruit (grape and orange juice), red wine, whole milk.</p>	<p>Important: Please keep reminding the participant that this question is directed at the time before sampling. Barley coffee is also known as Caffè d’orzo.</p>
---	---	--	--

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	ASSOCIATED SUBSTANCE GROUP(S)	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>Do you drink tea (do not refer to herbal infusions)</p> <p>If the answer is yes, did you drink the following types of tea during the 48 hrs prior to sampling?</p> <p>Total number of cups in the last 48hrs (Black tea and green tea)</p>	<p>Arsenic is a naturally occurring element that can be found in soil and water. Tea plants have the ability to absorb and accumulate arsenic from the soil.</p> <p>Tea leaves may be exposed to pesticides during cultivation to protect against pests and diseases. Residual amounts of pesticides can remain on the tea leaves and end up in the final product.</p>	<p>Arsenic and heavy metals, pesticides</p>	<p>Note the total number of cups of green and black tea consumed in the last 48 hrs.</p>
<p>Before providing the sample, when did you last drink water from wells and artesian wells?</p>	<p>Wells and artesian wells draw water from underground aquifers, which can be influenced by natural and activities sources of contamination. In agricultural areas, the use of fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides can potentially result in the contamination of groundwater</p>	<p>Heavy metals Pesticides</p>	<p><i>An artesian well</i> refers to a well from which water flows under natural pressure without pumping.</p>

Recent exposures questions to participants - Lifestyles

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	ASSOCIATED SUBSTANCE GROUP(S)	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>Have you been exposed to tobacco smoke during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?</p> <p>How many cigarettes during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?</p> <p>How long have you been exposed to second hand smoking during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?</p> <p>Have you been exposed to electronic cigarettes vapors during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?</p> <p>How many puffs of e-cigarettes did you take during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?</p> <p>Have you been exposed to electronic cigarettes vapors during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?</p> <p>Have you been exposed to second hand vape smoke during the <u>24 hrs</u> prior to sampling?</p>	<p>Exposure to tobacco smoke by smoking and passive exposure to tobacco smoke is a source of exposure to various substances. Similar to traditional cigarettes, e-cigarettes can emit secondhand aerosol that contains harmful substances, including nicotine and fine particles. Non-users who are exposed to secondhand aerosol may be at risk of adverse health effects, especially in enclosed spaces with poor ventilation.</p>	<p>Heavy Metals PAHs Tobacco-specific Nitrosamines Nicotine e-cigarettes and smokeless products often contain flavorings and additives</p>	<p>The question aims at both active smoking/vaping and passive smoking/vaping (= exposure to second hand smoke). Passive smoking means that the participant was exposed to tobacco smoke but was not smoking herself/himself.</p>
<p>Have you used any smokeless tobacco products such as snuff/snus, dip, or chewing tobacco during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?</p>			<p>This refers to a variety of smokeless tobacco products delivered through oral mucosa or nasal cavity.</p>

ANNEX 3.4 TO AD4.1 – INTERVIEWER MANUAL FOR THE PARC GENERAL SURVEY

<p>How many loadings did you take during the <u>24 hrs prior to sampling?</u></p>			
<p>Did you take any medications during the past 24 hrs prior to sampling? If yes, Please specify</p>	<p>Certain medications can influence the metabolism, elimination, or distribution of chemicals in the body. They may alter the levels of specific substances being measured or affect the effect biomarkers used for exposure assessment. Researchers should take into account any potential medication-related confounding factors in their data analysis and interpretation.</p>	<p>E.g. Coatings of pills and capsules can be a source of exposure for phthalates and substitutes.</p>	<p>Record information about participants' medications use, including the name of the medication and the dosage if possible</p>
<p>During the past 24 hrs prior to sampling, did you undergo one or more of the following medical treatments?</p>	<p>Medical equipment (e.g. plastic tubes used for dialysis) can contain substances of interest.</p>	<p>Phthalates & substitutes</p>	<p>Dialysis is a treatment method for loss of kidney function. This question aims to clarify contact with (e.g. polyurethane) medical devices/plastics.</p>

Recent exposures questions to participants - Home exposures

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	ASSOCIATED SUBSTANCE GROUP(S)	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>Have you inhaled smoke from any of the following energy sources inside your home during the 24 hrs prior to sampling? Charcoal/Coal Wood (firewood, chips, pellets, etc.)</p>	<p>Combustion processes are a potential source of PAHs and heavy metals.</p>	<p>Heavy metals PAHs</p>	
<p>Have you used insecticide products to control or repel insects (including treatment of pets) at your house in the 48 hours prior to sampling? Please, consider insecticide sprays, tablets, liquids etc...</p> <p>Have you used insect repellents or anti-parasite products for human use (e.g. mosquitos, lice, ticks products...), during the past 48 hrs prior to sampling?</p> <p>Has your garden/vegetable garden been treated with pesticides in the last week (7 days)?</p>	<p>Recent exposure to insecticide products before HBM sampling provides valuable information to assess the immediate effects, potential levels of pesticide residues, and short-term exposure patterns. It allows for a more precise evaluation of individual exposure and its potential impact on biomonitoring results.</p>	<p>Pesticides</p>	<p>Record information on the use of the pesticides, insecticides in the different scenario</p>

References

- Abuawad, A., Spratlen, M.J., Parvez, F., Slavkovich, V., Ilievski, V., Lomax-Luu, A.M., Saxena, R., Shahriar, H., Nasir Uddin, M., Islam, T., Graziano, J.H., Navas-Acien, A., Gamble, M.V., 2021. Association between body mass index and arsenic methylation in three studies of Bangladeshi adults and adolescents. *Environ. Int.* 149, 106401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106401>
- Brinchmann, B.C., Le Ferrec, E., Bisson, W.H., Podechard, N., Huitfeldt, H.S., Gallais, I., Sergent, O., Holme, J.A., Lagadic-Gossmann, D., Øvrevik, J., 2018. Evidence of selective activation of aryl hydrocarbon receptor nongenomic calcium signaling by pyrene. *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 158, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcp.2018.09.023>
- Cantonwine, D.E., Meeker, J.D., Ferguson, K.K., Mukherjee, B., Hauser, R., McElrath, T.F., 2016. Urinary Concentrations of Bisphenol A and Phthalate Metabolites Measured during Pregnancy and Risk of Preeclampsia. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 124, 1651–1655. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP188>
- Chevrier, C., Béranger, R., 2018. Pesticides and Child's Health in France. *Curr. Environ. Health Rep.* 5, 522–530. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40572-018-0216-x>
- Fucic, A., Duca, R.C., Galea, K.S., Maric, T., Garcia, K., Bloom, M.S., Andersen, H.R., Vena, J.E., 2021. Reproductive Health Risks Associated with Occupational and Environmental Exposure to Pesticides. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 18, 6576. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18126576>
- Lum, K.J., Sundaram, R., Barr, D.B., Louis, T.A., Buck Louis, G.M., 2017. Perfluoroalkyl Chemicals, Menstrual Cycle Length, and Fecundity: Findings from a Prospective Pregnancy Study. *Epidemiol. Camb. Mass* 28, 90–98. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EDE.0000000000000552>
- Susmann, H.P., Schaidler, L.A., Rodgers, K.M., Rudel, R.A., 2019. Dietary Habits Related to Food Packaging and Population Exposure to PFASs. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 127, 107003. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP4092>

Arsenic Poisoning (2011) <https://calpoison.org/news/arsenic-poisoning-2011>

HBM4EU D14.2 <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-14-2-list-of-effect-biomarkers-for-the-first-set-of-prioritized-substances-september-2018/>

OECD/Eurostat/UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2015), “Summary table of ISCED 2011 codes and criteria”, in *ISCED 2011 Operational Manual: Guidelines for Classifying National Education Programmes and Related Qualifications*, OECD Publishing, Paris.

Pictures and information of the food gallery were extracted from the menuCH Swiss Picture Book issued for the Swiss nutritional survey. Thank you to **Natalie von Goetz** from the Federal Office of Public Health, Switzerland for sharing these documents for the elaboration of PARC questionnaires.

The seafood and fish portion sizes photo are copied from the HBM4EU-MOM study questionnaire.

Appendix A

Annex A

Summary table of ISCED 2011 codes and criteria

The units of the ISCED classification are education programmes and their related recognised qualifications.

<http://www.uis.unesco.org/Education/Pages/international-standard-classification-of-education.aspx>

The ISCED classification uses **3 digits**: the **first is the educational level**, the **second and third are complementary dimensions**.

The ISCED level of an education programme reflects the degree of complexity and specialisation of the content of the programme measured with respect to gradations of learning experiences and the knowledge, skills and competencies the programme is intended to impart. Educational attainment is measured with respect to the highest education programme successfully completed, which is normally certified by a recognised qualification. If the highest education programme is not successfully completed, the level of attainment of the person is their attainment level before entering the programme.

LEVELS AND COMPLEMENTARY DIMENSIONS OF THE INTERNATIONAL STANDARD CLASSIFICATION OF EDUCATION (ISCED) 2011

Codification of education programmes and educational attainment

Level		Criteria for classifying national programmes by levels	
1 st digit		Main criteria	Subsidiary criteria
No education		–	–
0	Early childhood education	<i>Learning stimulated by environment (§105)* or in interaction with educators (§106).</i>	<i>Qualifications of staff: Pedagogical qualifications for educators (§111).</i>
		<i>Institution: school-based or centre-based (§107)</i>	<i>Existence of a regulatory framework (§112).</i>
		<i>Admission/age: 3 years and above for pre-primary education (§102/108).</i> <i>Intensity: 2 hours of education per day and 100 days a year (§110).</i>	<i>Typically not compulsory (§113).</i>
1	Primary education	<i>Education with systematic teaching and learning in reading, writing and mathematics (§125).</i>	<i>Often coincides with the beginning of compulsory education (§127).</i>
		<i>Admission/age and duration: official age of entry between ages 5 and 7 years; typical duration of 6 years (range is 4 to 7 years) (§122).</i> <i>Teacher: typically one main teacher is in charge of a group (§126).</i>	
2	Lower secondary education	<i>Transition to subject-oriented instruction (§144).</i>	<i>Typical entry age is between 10 and 13 years, the most common being 12 (§141).</i>
		<i>Entry requirements: completion of primary education (or the capacity to study at ISCED level 2) (§145).</i>	<i>Subject teachers, with qualifications in specific subjects as well as pedagogy (§147).</i>
		<i>Cumulative duration: ends after 8 to 11 years of education (often 9) from the start of primary education (§146).</i>	<i>The end of the level often coincides with the end of compulsory education (§148).</i>

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

Complementary dimensions			Coding		
1 st digit	2 nd digit	3 rd digit	Education programmes ISCED-P (Annex II of ISCED 2011)	Educational attainment ISCED-A (Annex III of ISCED 2011)	EU Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL/HATVOC**
-	-	-	-	010	000
Type of education:					
1	Early childhood educational development (0 to 2 years)	-	-	010	-
2	Pre-primary education (from 3 years to the start of primary education)	-	-	020	000
-	-	-	-	100	100
Programme orientation:					
		Level completion and access to higher ISCED level:			
4	General	1	Insufficient for level completion or partial level completion (duration < 2 years or cumulative duration < 8 years since the start of ISCED level 1).	241, 251	100
		2	Partial level completion (intermediate programme with duration ≥ 2 years and cumulative duration ≥ 8 years).	242, 252	242, 252
5	Vocational	3	Level completion without direct access to ISCED 3 (duration ≥ 2 years, cumulative duration ≥ 8 years).	243, 253	243, 253
		4	Level completion with direct access to ISCED 3 (duration ≥ 2 years, cumulative duration ≥ 8 years).	244, 254	244, 254

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

Level		Criteria for classifying national programmes by levels	
1 st digit		Main criteria	Subsidiary criteria
3	Upper secondary education	Second/final stage of secondary education, in form of general or vocational programmes (§167).	More differentiated programmes: increased range of options and streams (§169). Teachers often more qualified with respect to the subject matter they teach than lower secondary teachers (§170).
		Entry requirements: completion of lower secondary education (or the capacity to study at ISCED level 3) (§168).	
		Cumulative duration: programmes end 12 or 13 years since the beginning of ISCED 1 (§164).	
4	Post-secondary non-tertiary education	Post-secondary education, generally vocational and terminal programmes preparing for the labour market; typically, not considered as tertiary education at the national level (§190).	
		Programmes which serve to broaden rather than deepen the knowledge, skills and competencies of participants. Often not significantly more advanced than programmes at ISCED level 3 (§191).	
		Entry requirements: completion of upper secondary education (§186).	
5	Short-cycle tertiary education	Programmes often designed to provide participants with professional knowledge, skills and competencies; may provide pathway to academic programmes (§207). More complex than levels 3 and 4 but less than 6 (§212).	Institutional transition points: often provided by different institutions from ISCED levels 6, 7 and 8 (§214).
		Entry requirements: successful completion of upper secondary or post-secondary non-tertiary education giving access to ISCED levels 5, 6 or 7 (§208).	
		Minimum duration: 2 years (§213).	
		Typical duration: 2 to 3 years (§213).	

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

Complementary dimensions			Coding			
2 nd digit	3 rd digit		Education programmes ISCED-P (Annex II of ISCED 2011)	Educational attainment ISCED-A (Annex III of ISCED 2011)	EU Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL/HATVOC**	
Programme orientation:		Level completion and access to higher ISCED level:				
4	General	1	Insufficient for level completion or partial level completion (duration < 2 years or cumulative duration < 11 years since the start of ISCED level 1).	341, 351	244, 254	200
		2	Partial level completion (intermediate programme with duration ≥ 2 years and cumulative duration ≥ 11 years).	342, 352	342, 352	302/1, 302/2
5	Vocational	3	Level completion without direct access to ISCED 3 (duration ≥ 2 years, cumulative duration ≥ 11 years).	343, 353	343, 353	303/1, 303/2
		4	Level completion with direct access to ISCED 5, 6 or 7 (duration ≥ 2 years, cumulative duration ≥ 11 years).	344, 354	344, 354	304/1, 304/2
Programme orientation:		Level completion and access to higher ISCED level:				
4	General	1	Insufficient for level completion (duration < 6 months)	441, 451	344 354	300/1, 300/2
5	Vocational	3	Level completion without direct access to ISCED 5, 6 or 7	443, 453	443, 453	400/1, 400/2
		4	Level completion with direct access to ISCED 5, 6 or 7	444, 454	444, 454	
Programme orientation:		Level completion and access to higher ISCED level:				
4	General (or academic)	1	Insufficient for level completion (duration < 2 years)	541, 551	444, 454	400
5	Vocational (or professional)	4	Level completion	544, 554	540, 550	500

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

ANNEX A: SUMMARY TABLE OF ISCED 2011 CODES AND CRITERIA

Level		Criteria for classifying national programmes by levels	
1 st digit		Main criteria	Subsidiary criteria
6	Bachelor's or equivalent	Programmes often designed to provide participants with intermediate academic or professional knowledge, skills and competencies, leading to a first degree, such as a Bachelor's, or to an equivalent qualification (§224).	The requirement of a doctorate (ISCED level 8) qualification for some of the teaching staff may help distinguish ISCED levels 5 and 6 (§231).
		Entry requirements: successful completion of upper secondary or post-secondary non-tertiary education giving access to ISCED levels 5, 6 or 7; may require the passing of an entrance examination (§226).	Further studies: does not give direct access (usually) to doctoral programmes (ISCED level 8) (§226).
		Minimum cumulative duration of first degrees: 3 to 4 years full-time (§229). Position in the national degree structure: typically a first degree in tertiary education; sometimes a second degree of 1 to 2 years (§230).	
7	Master's or equivalent	Programmes often designed to provide participants with advanced academic or professional knowledge, skills and competencies, leading to a second degree, such as a Master, or to an equivalent qualification (§241).	Minimum duration of long 1 st degree: 5 years; complexity of content comparable to a Master's (§247).
		Position in the national degree structure: typically a second or further degree in tertiary education following a first degree at ISCED level 6 or 7 (§248) or a long first degree of at least 5 years if equivalent to a Master's in terms of the complexity of content (e.g. medicine) (§247). Entry requirements: in the case of a 2 nd degree, the successful completion of a Bachelor's or equivalent (ISCED level 6) or a Master's or equivalent (ISCED level 7) is required; in the case of a 1 st degree, the successful completion of upper secondary or of ISCED 4 granting access to tertiary education is required and, eventually, an entry examination (§243).	Further studies: often gives direct access to doctoral programmes (ISCED level 8) (§249).
8	Doctoral or equivalent	Its successful completion requires the submission of a thesis or an equivalent written work, of publishable quality, which is the output of original research representing a considerable contribution to knowledge in the field (§264). Entry requirements: the successful completion of an ISCED 7 programme (§261). Minimum duration: at least 3 years of full-time studies and a total cumulative duration of at least 7 years of tertiary education (§266).	Degree gives access to faculty positions and research posts (§266).

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.
** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

Complementary dimensions			Coding			
2 nd digit	3 rd digit		Education programmes ISCED-P (Annex II of ISCED 2011)	Educational attainment ISCED-A (Annex III of ISCED 2011)	EU Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL/HATVOC**	
Programme orientation:		Position in the national degree and qualification structure:				
4	Academic	1	Insufficient for level completion (duration of first degree < 3 years)	641, 651, 661	540, 550	500
5	Professional	5	First degree (at Bachelor's level) (duration 3 to 4 years)	645, 655, 665	640, 650, 660	600
6	Unspecified	6	Long first degree (at Bachelor's level) (duration > 4 years)	646, 656, 666		
		7	Second or further degree (following a 1 st degree at Bachelor's level)	647, 657, 667		
Programme orientation:		Position in the national degree and qualification structure:				
4	Academic	1	Insufficient for level completion (duration of first degree < 5 years)	741, 751, 761	640, 650, 660	600
5	Professional	6	Long first degree (at Master's level) (duration ≥ 5 years)	746, 756, 766	740, 750, 760	700
6	Unspecified	7	Second or further degree (following a 1 st degree at Bachelor's level)	747, 757, 767		
		8	Second or further degree (following a 1 st degree at Master's level)	748, 758, 768		
Programme orientation:		Position in the national degree and qualification structure:				
4	Academic	1	Insufficient for level completion (duration of first degree < 3 years)	841, 851, 861	740, 750, 760	700
5	Professional	4	Level completion	844, 854, 864	840, 850, 860	800
6	Unspecified					

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

Please cite this chapter as:

OECD/Eurostat/UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2015), "Summary table of ISCED 2011 codes and criteria", in *ISCED 2011 Operational Manual: Guidelines for Classifying National Education Programmes and Related Qualifications*, OECD Publishing, Paris.

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264228368-14-en>

Appendix B1

Definitions of major groups, sub-major groups

ISCO 2008

**STRUCTURE OF THE INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD CLASSIFICATION OF
OCCUPATIONS (ISCO-08)**

Major Groups

1. Managers
2. Professionals
3. Technicians and Associate Professionals
4. Clerical Support Workers
5. Services and Sales Workers
6. Skilled Agricultural, Forestry and Fishery Workers
7. Craft and Related Trades Workers
8. Plant and Machine Operators and Assemblers
9. Elementary Occupations
0. Armed Forces Occupation

Major and Sub-major Groups

1. *Managers*

11 Chief Executives, Senior Officials and Legislators

12 Administrative and Commercial Managers

13 Production and Specialized Services Managers

14 Hospitality, Retail and Other Services Managers

2. *Professionals*

21 Science and Engineering Professionals

22 Health Professionals

23 Teaching Professionals

24 Business and Administration Professionals

25 Information and Communications Technology Professionals

26 Legal, Social and Cultural Professionals

3. *Technicians and Associate Professionals*

31 Science and Engineering Associate Professionals

32 Health Associate Professionals

33 Business and Administration Associate Professionals

34 Legal, Social, Cultural and Related Associate Professionals

35 Information and Communications Technicians

4. *Clerical Support Workers*

41 General and Keyboard Clerks

42 Customer Services Clerks

43 Numerical and Material Recording Clerks

44 Other Clerical Support Workers

5. *Services and Sales Workers*

51 Personal Services Workers

52 Sales Workers

53 Personal Care Workers

54 Protective Services Workers

6. Skilled Agricultural, Forestry and Fishery Workers

61 Market-oriented Skilled Agricultural Workers

62 Market-oriented Skilled Forestry, Fishery and Hunting Workers

63 Subsistence Farmers, Fishers, Hunters and Gatherers

7. Craft and Related Trades Workers

71 Building and Related Trades Workers (excluding Electricians)

72 Metal, Machinery and Related Trades Workers

73 Handicraft and Printing Workers

74 Electrical and Electronic Trades Workers

75 Food Processing, Woodworking, Garment and Other Craft and Related Trades Workers

8. Plant and Machine Operators and Assemblers

81 Stationary Plant and Machine Operators

82 Assemblers

83 Drivers and Mobile Plant Operators

9. Elementary Occupations

91 Cleaners and Helpers

92 Agricultural, Forestry and Fishery Labourers

93 Labourers in Mining, Construction, Manufacturing and Transport

94 Food Preparation Assistants

95 Street and Related Sales and Services Workers

96 Refuse Workers and Other Elementary Workers

0. Armed Forces Occupations

01 Commissioned Armed Forces Officers

02 Non-commissioned Armed Forces Officers

03 03 Armed Forces Occupations, Other R

Appendix B2

**The Statistical classification of economic activities in the European
Community, abbreviated as NACE
(Type of industry/workplace)**

Type of industry/workplace

A – Agriculture, forestry and fishing;

- 01 Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities
- 02 Forestry and logging
- 03 Fishing and aquaculture

B – Mining and quarrying;

- 05 Mining of coal and lignite
- 06 Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas
- 07 Mining of metal ores
- 08 Other mining and quarrying
- 09 Mining support service activities

C – Manufacturing;

- 10 Manufacture of food products
- 11 Manufacture of beverages
- 12 Manufacture of tobacco products
- 13 Manufacture of textiles
- 14 Manufacture of wearing apparel
- 15 Manufacture of leather and related products
- 16 Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of particles of straw and plaiting materials
- 17 Manufacture of paper and paper products
- 18 Printing and reproduction of recorded media
- 19 Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products
- 20 Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products
- 21 Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations
- 22 Manufacture of rubber and plastic products
- 23 Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products
- 24 Manufacture of basic metals
- 25 Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment
- 26 Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products
- 27 Manufacture of electrical equipment
- 28 Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c.
- 29 Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers
- 30 Manufacture of other transport equipment

- 31 Manufacture of furniture
- 32 Other manufacturing
- 33 Repair and installation of machinery and equipment
- D – Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply;**
- 35 Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply
- E – Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation activities;**
- 36 Water collection, treatment and supply
- 37 Sewerage
- 38 Waste collection, treatment and disposal activities; materials recovery
- 39 Remediation activities and other waste management services
- F – Construction;**
- 41 Construction of buildings
- 42 Civil engineering
- 43 Specialised construction activities
- G – Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicle and motorcycles;**
- 45 Wholesale and retail trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles
- 46 Wholesale trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles
- 47 Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles
- H – Transportation and storage;**
- 49 Land transport and transport via pipelines
- 50 Water transport
- 51 Air transport
- 52 Warehousing and support activities for transportation
- 53 Postal and courier activities
- I – Accommodation and food service activities;**
- 55 Accommodation
- 56 Food and beverage service activities
- J – Information and communication;**
- 58 Publishing activities
- 59 Motion picture, video and television programme production, sound recording and music publishing activities
- 60 Programming and broadcasting activities
- 61 Telecommunications
- 62 Computer programming, consultancy and related activities
- 63 Information service activities

- K – Financial and insurance activities;**
- 64 Financial service activities, except insurance and pension funding
 - 65 Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding, except compulsory social security
 - 66 Activities auxiliary to financial services and insurance activities
- L – Real estate activities;**
- 68 Real estate activities
- M – Professional, scientific and technical activities;**
- 69 Legal and accounting activities
 - 70 Activities of head offices; management consultancy activities
 - 71 Architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis
 - 72 Scientific research and development
 - 73 Advertising and market research
 - 74 Other professional, scientific and technical activities
 - 75 Veterinary activities
- N – Administrative and support service activities;**
- 77 Rental and leasing activities
 - 78 Employment activities
 - 79 Travel agency, tour operator and other reservation service and related activities
 - 80 Security and investigation activities
 - 81 Services to buildings and landscape activities
 - 82 Office administrative, office support and other business support activities
- O – Public administration and defence, compulsory social security;**
- 84 Public administration and defence; compulsory social security
- P – Education;**
- 85 Education
- Q – Human health and social work activities;**
- 86 Human health activities
 - 87 Residential care activities
 - 88 Social work activities without accommodation
- R – Arts, entertainment and recreation;**
- 90 Creative, arts and entertainment activities
 - 91 Libraries, archives, museums and other cultural activities
 - 92 Gambling and betting activities
 - 93 Sports activities and amusement and recreation activities

S – Other service activities;

94 Activities of membership organisations

95 Repair of computers and personal and household goods

96 Other personal service activities

T – Activities of households as employers, undifferentiated goods – and services – producing activities of households for own use;

97 Activities of households as employers of domestic personnel

98 Undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activities of private households for own use

U – Activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies.

99 Activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies

Appendix C

Food portion sizes gallery

Pictures included in this gallery will be used to answer food consumption frequency questionnaire. These pictures will help to collect accurate measurements of portions sizes consumed by the participants. Please, indicate the portion sizes (A=small, B=medium, C=large) of each food item consumed in the last 4 weeks, according to the relationship with the food picture.

I. VEGETABLES

A

7 - 1

11 - 1

17 - 1

10 - 1

B

7 - 3

11 - 3

17 - 3

10 - 3

C

7 - 5

Spinach

11 - 5

Zucchini

17 - 5

Broccoli

10 - 5

Green beans

I. VEGETABLES

19 - 1

21 - 1

1 - 1

91 - 1

19 - 3

21 - 3

1 - 3

91 - 3

19 - 5

Sweet peas

21 - 5

Beans

1 - 5

Potatoes

91 - 5

Mushrooms

II. FRUITS

26 - 1

92-93 - 1

24 - 1

Strawberries -
Raspberries

26 - 3

Raisins -
Cherries

92-93 - 3

24 - 3

Peaches/A
pricots/Ap
nles

26 - 5

92-93 - 5

24 - 5

III. SEAFOOD - FISH

55 - 1

55 - 3

Canned Tuna

55 - 4

IV. MEAT

828 - 1

827 - 1

826 - 1

102 - 1

828 - 3

827 - 3

826 - 3

102 - 3

828 - 5

827 - 5

826 - 5

102 - 5

Steak

Ribs

Filet

Raw ground beef

832 - 1

838 - 1

833 - 1

832 - 3

838 - 3

833 - 3

832 - 5

838 - 5

833 - 5

Ham

Chicken nuggets

Bacon

V. DAIRY PRODUCTS (NOT SKIMMED) AND EGGS

813 - 1

57 - 1

302 - 1

813 - 3

57 - 3

302 - 3

813 - 5

Cheese

57 - 5

Butter

302 - 4

Eggs - omelets

VI. CEREALS

36 - 1

75 - 1

40 - 1

36 - 3

75 - 3

40 - 2

36 - 5

75 - 5

40 - 4

Rice

Pasta

Breakfast cereal
Cornflakes

V. MEAT SUBSTITUTES

23 - 1

23 - 3

23 - 4

Tofu

